

Scalable Data Profiling for Quality Analytics Extraction

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Abstract. In today’s modern society, data play an integral role in the development global industry, since they have become a valuable asset for companies, institutions, governments, and others. At the same time, data generated daily, at a global scale, require significant resources to pre-process, filter and store. When it comes to acquiring such stored data, it is essential to understand which dataset fits to the needs of the user beforehand. One particularly important factor is the quality of a dataset, which could be determined based on a series of quality related attributes generated by it. Such attributes constitute “Profiling”, the process of obtaining information from a data sample, related to the complete dataset’s quality. However, in the era of Big Data, the ability to apply profiling techniques in complete large datasets should also be considered, in order to obtain complete quality insights. This paper attempts to provide a solution for this consideration by presenting “DaQuE”, a scalable framework for efficient profiling and quality analytics extraction in complete datasets of all volumes.

Keywords: Big Data · Data profiling · Big Data analysis · Data quality

1 Introduction

Data is arguably one of the most precious assets in today’s fast evolving world [11]. In a society where technological advancements are more frequent than ever

[2], data generation and sharing are always parts of new products, technologies, services, systems and frameworks. This means that the amount of data generated daily, at a global scale, is massive. Latest estimations indicate that approximately 328.77 million terabytes of data are created each day [10]. The term “created” includes data that is newly generated, captured, copied, or consumed. All this huge amount of information can prove (and has already done) to be very valuable for many entities.

In the industry sector, businesses, irrespective of their size or domain, increasingly recognize the pivotal role that data plays in driving informed decision-making and gaining a competitive edge. For industries like finance, healthcare, and manufacturing, data serves as a catalyst for innovation, enabling the development of advanced analytics, predictive models, and automation systems that optimize operational processes. Moreover, marketing and retail sectors leverage data to understand consumer behavior, tailor personalized experiences, and refine targeted strategies. The intrinsic value of data is not limited to commercial enterprises alone; governmental bodies harness data to enhance public services, formulate evidence-based policies, and foster economic development. As the digital landscape continues to evolve, the significance of data transcends boundaries, becoming an indispensable resource for fostering growth, efficiency, and progress across diverse industry sectors.

Ensuring the quality of data is very important for all data recipients. In the realm of data-driven decision-making, the accuracy, reliability, and completeness of data directly (among other characteristics) influence the outcomes and insights derived from analytical processes. For data recipients, regardless of their role or entity (businesses, researchers, policymakers, analysts, scientists, and engineers etc.), relying on high-quality data is essential for making informed choices and implementing effective strategies. Inaccuracies or inconsistencies in data can lead to flawed analyses and misguided conclusions, potentially causing significant consequences. Therefore, the ability to obtain insights on a dataset’s quality is not just a best practice, but also a requirement in the dynamic landscape of data-driven decision-making. Taking into account all the aforementioned aspects, a solution that would be able to tackle the large volume of a dataset, but at the same provide complete quality insights to it, seems imperative.

Various approaches exist for extracting quality analytics from datasets. One of the most well-known ones is Data profiling. Different authors have given different definitions of what they describe as Data profiling. According to IBM [15], Data profiling is the process of reviewing and / or cleaning data, in order to enhance the understanding of its structure, and also uphold data quality standards within an organization. The primary objective is to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the data’s quality through methodologies that review and summarize it, followed by an evaluation of its overall condition. Factors like accuracy, consistency, and timeliness are considered during data profiling, in order to reveal any inconsistencies, inaccuracies, or the presence of null values in the data.

Taking all the aforementioned aspects into account, a scalable (or also volume-agnostic) Data profiling solution which will allow users to create their own quality rules (for customized quality analysis), should be thoroughly examined. This paper presents a profiler software tool for datasets of all volumes, including Big Data ones, which will be able to perform quality analysis in their entirety (in all the data of each set). The proposed framework's name is "*Data Quality Extractor*", or "*DaQuE*" for short. DaQuE will comply to the profiling definition provided, obtaining quality-related insights from datasets, allowing users to define their own quality standards, applying its techniques to whole sets, and operating in a low resource computational environment, thus being efficient.

The structure of this scientific paper unfolds as follows: Following the Introduction, the subsequent section delves into Related Work, offering an exploration of existing research and literature regarding Big Data-oriented profiling in complete datasets. The subsequent section meticulously details the proposed framework, providing an in-depth analysis of its two constituent flows, namely, "Data Profiler" and "Data Evaluator". The next section, DaQuE User Scenario in Telecommunications Domain, outlines a practical application scenario for the DaQuE framework. Finally, the paper concludes with a summary in the Conclusion section.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Data Profiling and Quality Analysis

The subject of Data Profiling has been extensively studied. Multiple implementations, publications and software solutions regarding profiling are widely available. The method of data sampling has proven to be a precise and effective process, which allows for exploratory data analysis, profiling and model prototyping on manageable subsets, leading to the ability of providing insights and validation before scaling up to larger datasets. However, when it comes to data profiling of large volumes, along with the ability to apply the profiling techniques to complete tabular datasets, the research results narrow down to a few similar proposals.

As far as proposed approaches for Big Data-oriented profiling in complete datasets go, one discussed in Dai et al.'s paper back in 2016 [9] seems to be similar to DaQuE. In their paper, the authors conducted a comprehensive review of existing literature, examining various works and analyzing their respective definitions of data profiling. They also put forth updated classifications for tasks associated with data profiling. Furthermore, the paper provided insights into several profiling tools available at the time, encompassing both free and commercial options. In addition, the authors introduced a set of new metrics for assessing data quality, along with a methodology for calculating data quality scores. Last but not least, the authors engaged in a discussion about a data profiling tool framework tailored for big data applications. However, the theoretical framework proposed would require a high-cost hardware infrastructure, since it needs a considerable amount of resources in order to be implemented. DaQuE's

approach is resource friendly and shall prove to achieve volume-agnostic data profiling, running at an average computer's hardware requirements.

In a publication made by Abedjan et al. in 2017 [1], the authoring team emphasized the significance of data profiling within the context of any data-related use-case, analyzing the domain of data profiling through a comprehensive examination of existing data profiling systems and methodologies. The team also focused to challenging issues in data profiling, encompassing topics like developing algorithms for dependency discovery and profiling algorithms tailored for dynamic data streams. In addition, they highlighted the importance of profiling in the era of Big Data, which — today — is more relevant than ever before. However, the researchers focused on analyzing the subject of data profiling itself, without examining its applications to Big Data sets. In fact, they included this topic as an open issue which should undergo future research.

A highly interesting implementation is one made by Taleb et al. in 2019 [25], which is a complete data quality profiling framework, based on the Big Data concept. More specifically, the authors introduced a Data Quality Profiling Model tailored for Big Data, comprising several modules such as sampling, profiling, exploratory quality profiling and quality profile repository. A series of experiments were undertaken to assess various facets of the framework, including sampling and profiling, and the aforementioned modules, all aimed at enhancing the quality of Big Data. Although an implementation that produced positive results, the research team focused on the — otherwise proven — "sampling and then profiling" approach. Therefore, they did not examine the case of applying profiling techniques to entire datasets.

A survey made by Liu and Zhang in 2020 [16] [17], focused on the exploration of sampling techniques for data profiling purposes within the realm of Big Data. It delves into the utilization of sampling across various data profiling categories. The findings derived from experimental analyses indicate that the outcomes obtained from sampled data closely match or even surpass those obtained from the entire dataset. As a result, the survey highlighted the significance of sampling technology when it comes to Big Data profiling. In addition, the research team hinted that they anticipate sampling technology to evolve into an essential facet of Big Data processing in the future. Although an interesting approach that exploits the benefits of sampling in Big Data profiling, occasions exist where the ability to apply profiling operations in whole datasets might be valuable for a company or a data engineer. This is what DaQuE aims to achieve.

An extensive theoretical analysis on Big Data profiling was made by Elbaghazaoui et al. in 2021 [12]. In their survey, the researchers aimed to underscore the significance of data profiling in general, and then provide insight into the domain of data profiling within the context of Big Data. They elaborated on various use cases of data profiling, examining existing systems and techniques employed in the field. The authors summarized by outlining challenges for prospective research in the realm of data profiling. Their theoretical work can prove to be helpful when conducting research towards the implementation of a volume-agnostic

data profiler (similar to what the current scientific aims to achieve), but they did not provide a complete solution for efficient profiling of such datasets.

Last but not least, a similar analysis with the one of Elbaghazaoui's was made by Couto et al. in 2022 [8]. The authoring team suggested that data scientists need to understand the characteristics of the data at hand, with the additional necessity of continually updating this knowledge to accommodate the continuous influx of new data. Based on this reasonable assumption, the authors conducted a comprehensive review of the existing literature, examining the utilization of data profiling within Big Data ecosystems. They studied papers that present emerging trends in Big Data profiling. They also categorized and reviewed the current advancements in Big Data profiling, considering prominent tools, scenarios, datasets, and the extracted metadata and information, before delving into potential future considerations and challenges of the field. Similar to [12], Couto's survey can be of high assistance in the early stages of research, towards the goal of proposing and implementing an efficient and scalable data profiler for quality analytics extraction.

2.2 User-Defined Quality Rules

The quality measurement process related to a well-known scenario and within a non-frequently changing data sources, is perfectly addressed with a pre-configuration of quality requirements, utilizing the common dimensions and metrics. Nevertheless, a situation where the quality requirements are established by different users with different data sources and needs, could better capitalize the possibility of creating user defined rules and metrics in a dynamic way.

So, apart from the automated process of Data Profiling and Quality Analysis, an insight should be provided on the ability of the end-user (whether it is a company, a data engineer or a consumer) to define their own quality standards / rules, in order to obtain deeper knowledge on specific quality aspects that they consider important. In a publication made by Anastasija Nikiforova in 2020 [21], the author describes a data object-driven approach to data quality evaluation, and proposes to substitute the concept of "quality dimensions" for "quality requirements", which basically introduces a level on top of the aforementioned dimensions.

These requirements are defined by the user, depending on their purposes. In a work published by Altendeitering et al. in 2024 [3], the researchers design a Software Reference Architecture for Data Quality Tools, after a thorough study of ten different data quality tools. The Architecture proposed includes a module for creating "user defined rules", as part of the Interaction Layer. These rules can be considered as an extension of the general data quality rules but applying some domain-specific constraints. The Rule Generation module will execute those constraints defined by the user.

It is clearly an advantage of a Data Quality evaluation when the users are allowed to introduce their perspective to accomplish the levels of quality that a particular scenario needs. The development of a complete and dynamic software

tool should consider the user an essential stakeholder in the Data Quality Evaluation process. The definition of user defined quality rules needs to be formalized and standardized, in order to be part of the quality information of the evaluated data and, therefore, ready to be understood transparently by the software tool itself. This could be achieved with the end-user defining the rules through a dashboard, with those rules being stored and executed as part of the profiling process.

3 Description of the Framework

3.1 Overview

The Data Quality Extractor aims to provide data professionals with a powerful insight on the quality of a selected dataset. Each user will select the dataset he/she wishes to conduct a quality analysis on, and then, the DaQuE will proceed to make a series of operations, extracting quality related analytics from it. Since such a task is a relatively mainstream one (in the field of Data Science), what differentiates the Data Quality Extractor from the majority of existing implementations, is its ability to extract analytics from whole datasets and not just samples (of those datasets). Furthermore, DaQuE will be able to seamlessly process all kinds of data volumes, adding a new perspective to the definition of classic data profiling.

Figure 1 presents the Data Quality Extractor’s architecture. In general, DaQuE will be initiated once the data recipient / end-user selects a dataset (available from a given data lake) for which he/she wishes to obtain quality analytics. Then, DaQuE will request that dataset (or a data sample, depending on the user’s choice) from the backend. When the dataset has been successfully retrieved, the first of DaQuE’s two flows will begin its operation. It is called “Data Profiler” and, after processing the dataset, what it does is *i)* apply generic quality rules to any requested dataset, *ii)* extract quality analytics based on those rules and then *iii)* forward the results to the end-user.

The user will then have information regarding the quality of the dataset he/she selected. This information will be the product of Data Profiler’s generic rules application. Based on the profile generated, the end-user will now have the opportunity to expand the analysis. A “rules’ creator” will give the user the ability to set their own specific rules, regarding the dataset already loaded to the Data Quality Extractor. Once the user sets all the new custom-made and specific rules, they will be sent back to DaQuE, initiating its second flow’s operation. This second flow is named “Data Evaluator” and is responsible for the expansion of the Data Profiler’s initial generated profile, based on the new specific quality rules given by the user. If needed, the Evaluator will process the selected dataset again. It will then proceed to *i)* apply the specific rules provided by the user, *ii)* make further quality filtering based on these rules and *iii)* forward the new information back to the frontend, as a template.

The research team’s goal is to develop DaQuE in a way that will be easy to be deployed by end-users. This means that it will have to be a highly efficient

Fig. 1. The architecture of Data Quality Extractor, along with its two operational flows, Data Profiler and Data Evaluator.

software tool, demanding relatively low computer resources that can be found in a consumer-grade physical machine. The plan is to use an average CPU with a maximum of 6 cores, and 5 GB's of RAM. This is considered as part of the standard equipment in budget PCs. The success threshold set by the research team, is for DaQuE to apply its quality-related operations in a Big Data set and produce the final profile, with a speed of 1 GB per 1 minute (1GB/Min). The speed limit set, combined with the budget-friendly resources for testing, shall highlight (or abate) DaQuE's ability to profile complete larger datasets efficiently, being an easily deployable software tool for consumers. In order to achieve the speed limit / success threshold, inspiration shall be drawn from the implementation of a Big Data processing framework (for Critical Infrastructure datasets), developed by members of the current research team in 2023 [22]. The

conceptual basis of both the current and the aforementioned work is a research by Marinakis et al., published in 2022 [19].

3.2 Framework Operational Flows

Data Profiler

The Data Profiler is the Data Quality Extractor’s first component, in terms of the operation process flow. It is the first component of DaQuE to start its procedure, when the end-user selects a dataset for profiling. Depending on the user’s choice, whether he/she wishes to profile the whole dataset or a sample of it, DaQuE retrieves this dataset from a provided repository, and then the Data Profiler begins its operation, by proceeding to do the following steps (as seen in 1):

- Process the dataset received, following basic pre-processing steps for new incoming datasets.
- Retrieve the generic quality rules / KPIs, by reading / parsing a code file containing the pre-agreed upon selection of such rules.
- Apply the rules to the dataset, by matching each generic rule to its corresponding dataset column (eg. Timestamp-related rules will match Timestamp columns etc.). If a rule applies to all columns, the Profiler will do so.
- Extract profiling analytics based on the generic rules, gathering all the information necessary to build the quality profile for the dataset.
- Prepare the profile template, based on the quality analytics gathered.

Once the Data Profiler forwards the profile template to the end-user, it seizes its operation. It will function again, whenever the end-user wishes to initiate the whole process with a new dataset selection. Therefore, Data Profiler runs only once for every dataset selected, within a given session.

Data Evaluator

The Data Evaluator is the Data Quality Extractor’s second component, in terms of the operation process flow. It will initiate its operation only if the end-user decides to apply his/her own specific rules to the profiling, after the Data Profiler has completed its profile creation. Therefore, if the user decides to obtain a deeper insight to the selected dataset, using their own specific rules, then the Data Evaluator takes the spotlight. By the time all specific rules are submitted by the end-user, and as seen in 1, the Data Evaluator will proceed to complete the following steps:

- Check if new process of the dataset is needed. If so, begin a basic pre-processing of the dataset, similar to the Data Profiler.

- Retrieve the specific quality rules defined by the user, as they will be fed to the component by the platform’s frontend.
- Apply the newly retrieved rules to the dataset, matching each rule to its corresponding (dataset) field / column. Similar to the Profiler, if a rule applies to all columns, the Evaluator will do so.
- Conduct further quality filtering, based on the rules, and extract new quality-related analytics, in order to expand the existing dataset’s profile.
- Add the new information to the existing profile template, by updating it.

It is worth noting that the Data Evaluator can be triggered multiple times in one session. It all depends on the end-user and whether he/she wishes to constantly add new specific rules (and therefore apply them to the dataset), based on the feedback he/she gets from the Evaluator every time, or not. To sum up, unlike Data Profiler, which runs only once in every session (always in the beginning, when the end-user decides which dataset to extract quality analytics for), the Data Evaluator can be run as many times as the end-user wishes to.

3.3 Technologies To Use

In order to achieve optimal and efficient management of the whole process, the Data Quality Extractor will be developed upon the Apache Spark framework. This way, DaQuE will be able to fulfill the original commitment, which is to load and apply its profiling techniques to all kinds of data volumes, from smaller datasets and data samples to larger, big data ones. The programming language that will be used for the implementation of DaQuE’s Data Profiler and Data Evaluator will be Python, in order to benefit from its data science-oriented libraries and processing capabilities. The implementation plan is to build a standalone — but scalable nonetheless — Apache Spark instance (in one physical machine), where DaQuE’s Data Profiler and Evaluator will be triggered as Python written (PySpark), Spark jobs. Thus, the framework will always be available for communication with the end-users, achieving undistorted availability and high efficiency, in terms of processing big data volumes in low time. Last but not least, it is important to note that the Data Quality Extractor will be developed as a module of generic nature, keeping in mind that tabular datasets of various types should be supported.

Regarding the framework on which DaQuE will be built upon, considered solutions were Apache Spark [5], Apache Flink [4] and Apache Storm [6]. All three tools are widely recognized and extensively used in the Data industry. In the context of DaQuE’s data profiling tasks, Apache Spark is the final selection. Notably, it supports multiple programming languages (Java, Scala, Python, R), boasts comprehensive documentation, possesses a vast user community, and can generate advanced analytical results. A comparative analysis reveals distinct advantages and challenges for each framework. For instance, Storm is primarily designed for real-time data processing [14], and could be considered as the preferable choice. However, DaQuE focuses on the quality profiling of pre-existing /

historical data. In terms of batch data processing, both Spark and Flink demonstrate excellent performance, with each outshining the other depending on various benchmarks (e.g., data type, size, job pattern) [18] [26]. However, Spark exhibits superior scalability and overall faster runtimes [13]. Consequently, due to its scalability, richer analytical library, and extensive documentation, Spark was chosen over Flink and Storm.

Regarding the developing phase, Python [24] emerged as the preferred language for the implementation of DaQuE. Firstly, Python’s syntax is clean, concise, and readable, facilitating faster development and easier maintenance. Its extensive set of libraries and frameworks, such as NumPy, Pandas, and SciPy, provide robust support for data manipulation and analysis, crucial for Big Data processing, analysis, and other applications [20]. When it comes to parallel and distributed computing, Python’s popularity is further amplified by its compatibility with Apache Spark, through PySpark [7] (Python’s API for Spark). This integration enables developers to harness Spark’s capabilities for large-scale data processing, while leveraging Python’s simplicity and ease of use. As a result, Python is selected as the preferred language for the development of DaQuE.

4 User Scenario in Telecommunications Domain

Critical Infrastructures (CI’s) are entities whose data can vary in terms of features, formats, volumes and types. Sometimes, the data generation levels of CI’s can reach very high volumes, making the adoption of scalable data processing solutions a crucial step, in order to successfully implement a data quality analytics extraction tool. Sometimes, several limitations might occur during the process of data preparation (e.g., anonymization) by the CI sector entities, since information need to be filtered before being made available for a software tool like the the Data Quality Extractor. However, the operation of data profiling is crucial for a CI, for it to obtain deeper insights on the quality of their data assets.

The Telecommunications Sector is one CI example where data diversity is evident. In this case, the high volumes of data is highlighted. More specifically, OTE Group [23] is the largest Telecommunications provider in Greece, with over seven million subscribers, offering convergent services such as fixed-line and mobile telephony, broadband services, and pay-tv for their retail (B2C and B2B) clients. On top of those, the organization offers additional services to cover integrated ICT solutions (focusing on B2B clients), insurance and electronic transactions, online payments and delivery of merchandise and food. Apparently, all those business activities rely heavily on large amounts of information that is being produced on a regular basis. For instance, the volume of data that is needed to describe: i) details of user product status, ii) events of assignment products to the users, iii) changes in product components, iv) requests for promos and special offers, and v) events for rate plan changes, concerning only a six-months period is more than 1.3 Terabytes of data. To this end, the growing demand on

having data-driven decision making, increases the need to access high-quality data, derived from heterogeneous data sources, in an efficient and scalable way.

According to the current business processes that have been established inside the company, data owners and consumers perform data quality checks only in the consumption point (reactive checks). With this kind of ad-hoc analysis, the resolution of data quality issues takes a lot of time and effort. Through the proposed framework, users would be able to execute commonly agreed data quality checks, as these have been requested from the data owners, and the extracted analytics report would then be proactively available to the data consumers, enabling them to understand if the available data is ready to be consumed, taking also into account freshness and data synchronization aspects of the information. Consequently, decisions makers would feel confident to exploit the available datasets, knowing that the required quality level is being guaranteed, and the data to be used meet the necessary standards. Furthermore, the feature of having a global point to define data quality business rules in a user-friendly manner, is of high significance. Given the fact that OTE Group consists of many subsidiaries companies that have their own data stores without common principles, this format and volume-agnostic module will allow business users to monitor key data elements, simply by applying centralized quality rules for every data source, eliminating the need for replicating actions.

For example, when onboarding a new customer or renewing the product contract of an existing one, the ending date of that contract should obviously be later than its activation date. By applying the rule depicted in Figure 2, the Data Quality Extractor's Evaluator operational flow would be able to detect those kinds of inconsistent values.

```
{
  "rule_name": "customer_product_contract_dates_rule",
  "rule": {
    "subject_column": "Contract_End_Date",
    "object_column": "Contract_Activated",
    "column_datatype": "DATE",
    "logical_operator": ">"
  }
}
```

Fig. 2. High-level approach of a user-generated rule, regarding the contract dates of customers' products.

Moreover, the billing system of the company does not allow a customer to pay a bigger amount of money, compared to the total amount billed to his/her account, unless he/she exclusively makes a request for deposit balance. Figure 3 shows the corresponding rule that should be applied by DaQuE's Evaluator, in order to identify those cases.

```

{
  "rule_name": "customer_account_billing_amount_rule",
  "rule": {
    "subject_column": "Total_Billed",
    "object_column": "Total_Paid",
    "column_datatype": "NUMBER",
    "logical_operator": ">="
  }
}

```

Fig. 3. High-level approach of a user-generated rule, filtering the amount paid by customers' accounts.

5 Conclusion

The Data Quality Extractor can prove to be a new alternative in the field of Data Profiling and Quality Analysis. Its ability to apply profiling techniques to complete datasets, allow users to define their own quality rules, as well as be volume-agnostic, can make it a valuable solution for data analysts and engineers. Furthermore, the results drawn from its operation, shall provide a full insight on the advantages of profiling whole datasets. As mentioned earlier, DaQuE's development will be based on the implementation proposed by authors of the current research team [22]. This Big Data management framework, published in 2023, shares two similar goals to DaQuE, which are the low resource allocation and expected processing speed of 1GB/min.

Open Issues In order to develop the Data Quality Extractor, two main issues that will have to be resolved. First, further research shall be conducted regarding the Data Quality Extractors first operational flow, the Data Profiler. The automated profiling KPIs that will be selected, will have to be carefully examined, in order to ensure that all quality-related aspects of a dataset are covered. The Data Profiler will include a code section which will parse other code files, containing KPIs. Each file will be a KPI library, containing KPIs in the form of code. Then, the Data Profiler shall parse this library / code file, applying the KPI's to the incoming dataset and proceed with the profiling generation.

The second open issue is about the optimal implementation of DaQuE's second operational flow, the Data Evaluator. Since the Evaluator will apply user-generated profiling rules to the dataset, a specific rule format will have to be adopted. The end-user shall be able to create rules, but only within a well specified rule structure. Therefore, a rule structure will have to be defined, for both the user to know how to generate a new profiling rule, and the system to parse each rule properly. The structure / format could be similar to the KPI library / code file parsed by the Data Profiler, but that remains to be finalized.

Future Work After addressing and resolving the aforementioned open issues, the current research team shall initiate DaQuE's development. The software

tool will be implemented using Apache Spark and Python. Further additions of libraries and frameworks are yet to be determined. When the system is ready for deployment and testing, the research team shall proceed to collect datasets from various sources, in order to fully test DaQuE's capabilities. A performance analysis shall be made on the system itself, as well as its results. Both aspects (system's performance and results produced) will be assessed, in order to further improve DaQuE where needed.

The Data Quality Extractor, through his two operational flows, Data Profiler and Data Evaluator, can become a vital tool for Data Analytics and Profiling. Through its unique ability to process whole datasets - even Big Data ones - and provide quality-related insights, DaQuE may prove to be an important assistant to data engineers and analysts. Its final implementation shall provide a definitive answer as to whether the proposed approach is indeed feasible or not. However, the current research team is confident of the software tool's feasibility, having thoroughly studied several aspects of it (technologies to use, features, open issues, implementations to base the development on), which led to the establishment of an initial architecture (Figure 1). Is DaQuE a good alternative to the existing Data Profiling frameworks? The answer will be given by DaQuE itself.

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